

Analysis of the Relationship between the Utilization of Green Open Spaces (RTH) and the Level of Economic-Social Satisfaction of the Community in Mataram City

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the relationship between the utilization of Green Open Spaces (RTH) and the socio-economic satisfaction of the community in Mataram City. RTH utilization was measured through visit frequency, types of activities, and duration of use, while socio-economic satisfaction included perceptions of economic benefits, social well-being, and surrounding environmental quality. A quantitative correlational approach was employed with 30 respondents selected through accidental sampling. Data were collected using a Likert-scale questionnaire and analyzed through descriptive statistics and multiple linear regression. The findings indicate that both RTH utilization (X_1) and RTH quality/accessibility (X_2) have a positive and significant influence on socio-economic satisfaction (Y), with an R^2 value of 0.931. The strongest contribution comes from RTH quality/accessibility ($B = 0.680$), highlighting that facility conditions and accessibility play a crucial role in enhancing community well-being. These results suggest that optimizing social functions and the design quality of RTH can enhance urban socio-economic benefits. This study provides empirical insights for local governments in developing adaptive, inclusive, and community-oriented green spaces.

Keywords: *green open space, socio-economic satisfaction, environmental quality, multiple linear regression, Mataram City.*

Introduction

Green Open Space (RTH) is understood as an element of urban spatial planning that provides ecological, social, and economic functions, such as microclimate control, pollutant absorption, recreational space, and a place for social interaction (F. R. Muhammad et al., 2024). The concept of green space utilization encompasses quantitative dimensions (area, availability of facilities) and qualitative dimensions (quality of maintenance, accessibility, and suitability of function to residents' needs) that determine the intensity and patterns of community use of green spaces (Setyowati, 2008).

The economic and social satisfaction of communities in relation to the urban environment is often measured through indicators of life satisfaction, perceptions of economic benefits (e.g., business opportunities, increased property values), and subjective well-being influenced by public facilities, including green open spaces (Kwon, Hong, Yang, Wohn, Jung, et al., 2021). The theory of the relationship between public facilities and welfare states that, in addition to its ecological function, green space can improve quality of life and economic and social indicators by enhancing environmental comfort, informal economic opportunities, and psychosocial well-being (Zhang & Adam, 2024).

Empirical evidence shows a positive relationship between the use of green open spaces and various aspects of well-being. Cross-country studies have found a correlation between urban green space and happiness/quality of life (Kwon, Hong, Yang, Wohn, & Jung, 2021). WTP (willingness to pay) and life satisfaction studies in several cities show that access to and use of green open spaces contribute to the economic value perceived by the community and their willingness to support the financing of green open space maintenance (Kalfas et al., 2022). These results imply that the intensity of use and quality of green spaces are closely related to users' socio-economic perceptions.

Contextual studies in Indonesia confirm these findings on a local scale: a study evaluating Green Open Spaces (GOS) in Jakarta shows the contribution of green spaces to life satisfaction and housing economic indicators (Setiowati & Koestoer, 2024). Analysis of the use and socioeconomic impact of green spaces in several Indonesian cities also highlights that management, facilities, and community involvement determine the economic benefits that can be realized. In addition, case studies in a number of cities confirm that when green spaces are optimized, micro-businesses and informal economic activities around parks receive direct benefits (studies of maximizing social-economic impacts).

However, not all studies found a simple or linear relationship. Several studies showed that demographic factors, income, individuals' attachment to nature, and the quality of green space design moderated the effect of green space on economic and social satisfaction (Dmitrovi, 2025). Furthermore, studies on 'publicness' and accessibility indicate that the

physical availability of green spaces does not necessarily translate into high usage or social benefits if social aspects (safety, community acceptance, management) are neglected (A. R. Muhammad et al., 2025). In other words, the socio-economic benefits of green spaces are contextual and influenced by institutional and design factors..

Analysis of the above findings reveals a pattern: many international/national studies confirm the potential of green spaces to improve well-being and subjective economic value, but the final results are highly dependent on the quality of management, accessibility, and the socio-economic characteristics of users (see researchers cited in paragraphs 3–5). This raises two research gaps: (1) few studies have examined the direct relationship between the use (behavioral use metrics) of green spaces and socio-economic satisfaction indicators on a small/medium city scale in Indonesia (e.g., Mataram City) using a quantitative questionnaire-based approach that controls for demographic variables and usage characteristics; (2) the need for novelty that links actual utilization measures (frequency of visits, types of activities) with dimensions of economic-social satisfaction (satisfaction with income related to activities in RTH, perception of local economic opportunities, and social satisfaction) simultaneously. Therefore, research that measures green space utilization in detail and examines its impact on economic-social satisfaction in the context of Mataram City will fill this gap and provide contextual empirical evidence for welfare-based green space planning (Setiowati & Koestoer, 2024).

Based on this gap, the objectives of this study are: to analyze the relationship between the use of green open spaces (frequency of visits, types of activities, and duration) and the level of socio-economic satisfaction of the community in Mataram City, taking into account demographic control variables (income, age, education). The expected benefits of this research are: (a) to provide empirical evidence for city planners and the environmental/landscaping agency of Mataram City to design GO that is more responsive to the economic and social needs of residents; (b) contribute to the national literature on measuring the utilization of green open spaces and their impact on welfare; and (c) recommend community-based management and intervention strategies to maximize the economic and social benefits of green open spaces.

Research Method

This study uses a quantitative approach with a correlational type, which aims to determine the relationship between the variable of Green Open Space (GOS) utilization and the level of socio-economic satisfaction of the community in Mataram City. The quantitative approach was chosen because it is able to measure the relationship between variables objectively through numerical data processing and statistical analysis. The correlational type

was used to determine the extent of the relationship between the utilization of GOA (independent variable) and the economic-social satisfaction of the community (dependent variable), both in terms of the direction and strength of the relationship. This study focused on the community using GOA in the Mataram City area, as a representation of an urban community with diverse socio-economic activities.

The data sources for this study consist of primary data obtained directly from the community through the distribution of questionnaires, and secondary data derived from official local government documents or publications and literature related to green space management. The research sample consisted of 100 respondents who were green space users in Mataram City, selected using accidental sampling, i.e., any residents who were present and using the green space at the time the data was collected. This sample selection was conducted to obtain a representative picture of the community's perceptions and level of satisfaction regarding the use of green spaces in urban areas.

The research instrument used was a closed questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale, in which respondents were asked to provide answers based on their level of agreement with each statement (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree). There were a total of 18 statements, consisting of 6 items for variable X_1 (RTH Utilization) which assessed the aspects of frequency, intensity, and type of activities in RTH; 6 items for variable X_2 (Quality or Accessibility of RTH) covering ease of access, comfort, and supporting facilities; and 6 items for variable Y (Economic-Social Satisfaction) measuring perceptions of economic benefits, social welfare, and satisfaction with the surrounding environment. Each statement item was compiled based on theoretical indicators relevant to previous research.

The research procedure was carried out in several stages, namely: (1) preparation of instruments based on theoretical studies and content validation; (2) data collection through the distribution of questionnaires to respondents who met the criteria; (3) tabulation of data to ensure the completeness and accuracy of the results; (4) data analysis using descriptive statistics to describe the characteristics of respondents and the distribution of answers, and multiple linear regression analysis to test the relationship between the use of green space (X_1 and X_2) and the level of socio-economic satisfaction of the community (Y); (5) interpretation of the analysis results to draw substantive meaning from the relationships found; and (6) preparation of conclusions and recommendations based on the research results. The analysis was carried out using statistical software to obtain accurate and scientifically accountable results.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Statistics

A descriptive analysis of 30 respondents provides an initial picture of the community's perceptions of the utilization of green space (X_1), the quality/accessibility of green space (X_2), and the level of economic and social satisfaction (Y). The average values of X_1 and X_2 are 21.47 and 22.23, respectively, indicating that the intensity of use and perceived quality of green space are in the fairly good category. Meanwhile, the variable Y has an average of 23.30, indicating that the community's socio-economic satisfaction is relatively high.

The relatively wide score range (minimum 6–9 and maximum 30) on all three variables indicates variation in experiences and assessments among RTH users. The large standard deviation, especially on variable Y ($SD = 7.544$), confirms that the level of economic-social satisfaction is influenced by various socio-economic factors and characteristics of RTH use.

To obtain an initial overview of the research data trends, descriptive statistical analysis was performed on the three main variables, namely the utilization of Green Open Space (X_1), the quality/accessibility of Green Open Space (X_2), and the level of socio-economic satisfaction of the community (Y). This analysis aimed to examine the distribution of values, average trends, and variations in the scores given by respondents for each variable measured. The following descriptive statistics provide information on the minimum, maximum, average, and standard deviation values, which form the basis for understanding the characteristics of the data before conducting further analysis such as regression testing.

Tabel 1.Deskriptif Statistic

<i>Descriptive Statistics</i>			
	X 1	X 2	Y
Valid	30	30	30
Missing	0	0	0
Mean	21.47	22.23	23.30
Std. Deviation	5.513	6.191	7.544
Minimum	9.000	9.000	6.000
Maximum	30.00	30.00	30.00

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results

The regression model used aims to examine the contribution of X_1 (RTH Utilization) and X_2 (RTH Quality/Accessibility) to Y (Economic-Social Satisfaction). The summary of the results is as follows :

Model Summary

Model M_1 shows a value of $R = 0.965$ and $R^2 = 0.931$, which means that 93.1% of the variation in economic-social satisfaction can be explained by the utilization of green space and the quality/accessibility of green space. This value is very high, indicating a strong relationship between the two independent variables and the dependent variable.

To determine the extent to which the variables of green space utilization and green space quality/accessibility contribute to explaining variations in the economic and social satisfaction of the community, multiple linear regression analysis was performed. A summary of the test results is shown in the following Model Summary table. This table presents the correlation coefficient (R), coefficient of determination (R^2), and Adjusted R^2 values, which describe the strength and ability of the model in explaining the relationship between the research variables.

Tabel 2. Model Summary

Model Summary - Y

Model	R	R^2	Adjusted R^2	RMSE
M_0	0.000	0.000	0.000	7.544
M_1	0.965	0.931	0.926	2.050

Note. M_1 includes X_1, X_2

The Adjusted R^2 value = 0.926 confirms that the model remains stable even when taking into account the number of predictors.

ANOVA Test

The ANOVA results show an F value of 182.8 with $p < 0.001$, which means that the regression model is statistically significant. Thus, X_1 and X_2 are simultaneously proven to have a significant effect on Y . To ensure that the regression model used is valid and statistically significant, an ANOVA test was performed. This test aims to see whether the independent variables collectively have a significant effect on the dependent variable. The

ANOVA test results presented in the following table provide information about the significance of the regression model constructed.

Tabel 3. AnovaTest

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
M ₁	Regression	1536.8	2	768.406	182.8	<.001
	Residual	113.5	27	4.203		
	Total	1650.3	29			

Note. M₁ includes X 1, X 2

Note. The intercept model is omitted, as no meaningful information can be shown.

Regression Coefficient

The coefficient table shows that both independent variables have a positive and significant effect.

Tabel 4. Coefficient

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized	Standard Error	Standardized	t	p
M ₀	(Intercept)	23.300	1.377		16.917	<.001
M ₁	(Intercept)	-5.043	1.548		-3.257	.003
	X 1	0.616	0.124	0.450	4.974	<.001
	X 2	0.680	0.110	0.558	6.162	<.001

Based on the coefficient values, X₂ has a greater contribution ($\beta = 0.558$) than X₁ ($\beta = 0.450$), which means that perceptions of quality and access to green spaces are more decisive in determining the level of economic and social satisfaction than simply how often people use green spaces.

Discussion

The results of the study indicate that the utilization and quality of green spaces are significantly related to the level of economic and social satisfaction of the people of Mataram

City. These findings are in line with national and international studies which state that green spaces are public facilities that not only serve an ecological function, but also contribute to the psychosocial and economic well-being of the community.

The Effect of Green Space Utilization on Economic-Social Satisfaction

The positive coefficient ($B = 0.616$) indicates that the more often people visit and engage in activities in green spaces, the higher their level of economic and social satisfaction. This may be related to:

- Increased opportunities for social interaction,
- Opportunities for informal economic activities,
- Improved psychological well-being through outdoor recreation.

These findings support literature such as Kwon, Hong, Yang, Wohn, Jung, et al., (2021), which states that the intensity of green space utilization increases the happiness and life satisfaction of urban communities.

The Effect of Green Space Quality/Accessibility on Economic-Social Satisfaction

Variable X_2 has a larger coefficient ($B = 0.680$), indicating that quality, comfort, and good access are the main determinants of economic-social satisfaction. The community not only needs spacious green spaces, but also:

- Adequate facilities (pedestrian paths, toilets, play areas),
- Safety and comfort,
- Good vegetation maintenance,
- Easy access from residential areas.

These results reinforce the studies by Dmitrović (2025) and Blancarte-Siqueiros et al. (2020), which explain the importance of design and accessibility aspects in increasing the socio-economic benefits of green spaces.

The Relevance of Research Results to the Context of Mataram City

Mataram City, as a medium-sized city with high economic and social intensity, requires green spaces that can serve recreational needs, social interaction, and informal economic activities. The high R^2 value indicates that the local characteristics of green space users in Mataram are highly sensitive to changes in facility quality and improvements in the social function of green spaces.

These results provide empirical evidence that green space development strategies in Mataram must emphasize:

- Improvement of facilities,
- Improvement of physical accessibility,
- Programs that support small social and economic activities (SMEs, small traders, communities).

Conclusion

This study proves that The utilization of green spaces (frequency of visits, types of activities, and duration) as well as the quality/accessibility of green spaces have a positive and significant relationship with the economic and social satisfaction of the people of Mataram City. The variable of green space quality/accessibility (X_2) has the greatest influence in the regression model, indicating that design, maintenance, facilities, and ease of access are key determinants of economic and social well-being. The regression model shows a very high strength of relationship ($R^2 = 0.931$), indicating that most of the variation in economic-social satisfaction can be explained by these two main variables. The Mataram City Government needs to prioritize improving the quality of green space facilities so that the economic and social benefits can be felt more widely. Local economic empowerment activities based on green spaces can be optimized through government support for MSMEs around city parks. Green spaces must be maintained as safe, comfortable, and inclusive spaces for social interaction. Future research could add moderating variables such as income, education, or psychological attachment to the environment. Analysis using a larger sample and covering several types of green spaces in Mataram City to improve the generalization of results.

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